

Research Article

Attitudes of Women Farmers towards Urban Agriculture in Somolu Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assesses the attitudes of women farmers towards urban agriculture in Somolu local government area of Lagos State. Fifty respondents were randomly selected from five extension blocks were purposively selected due to high concentrations of women involved in urban agriculture. The data obtained were analyzed with the aid of frequency count and percentages while chi-square was used to test the hypothesis.

The findings indicates that the women's' attitude to urban agriculture remains extremely negative. The statistical analysis performed on the respondents' attitude towards urban agriculture as a profession revealed that there was significant relationship to the respondents' age, marital status, educational level, years of experience and access to loan respectively while farm size, annual income, access to labour and access to inputs were statistically insignificant.

Key words: Urban agriculture, attitude and women farmers

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria women have always played a key role in the society and its economy. In fact they perform five multiple roles which include; mother (child-beater), producer of agricultural crops, home manager, community organizer and social, cultural and political activity. Danso et al (2004) agrees with the issue of gender disparities generally, and in urban agriculture in particular, when he has this to say: "The general conceptions that women are always at a disadvantage in terms of access to productive resources, extension services, marketing and credit and that they are not capable of doing similar farming activities need to be tested on case by case basis. Gender analysis in urban agriculture is essential for policy formulation and programme planning to ensure equity in resource allocation and a balanced development that benefits both male and Women urban dwellers."

Many studies in developing countries has shown that women contribute as much or more than men do for the family food security and children's nutritional status when unpaid works are included in the estimation. Regardless of the level of development achieved by the respective economies, women play a pivotal role in agriculture and in rural development in most countries of the Africa Region. Urban women are likely to work for income when their children are very young and to stay in the labour force longer than they were previously. The percentage of households that rely on women's financial contribution for food security has also increased and women are contributing a higher percentage of income than before (Jeanne, 2000).

Pienaar and Anderson (2004) recommends that women predominate in urban agriculture which conveniently enables them to earn income, improve household diets, perform household chores, budgets and decision making. Involvement in urban agriculture has been introduced as a strategy used by the poor urban population to cope with food crisis. Pienaar and Anderson (2004) further stated that not all cities in the developing world show the same degree of agricultural activities. Increasing farming activities in the cities are closely linked to economic decline and increasing poverty in urban centres in most African countries.

Urban agriculture is a new phenomenon, perhaps due to the fact that in urban settings, there used to be no land that is allocated for agricultural purposes, but seeing that people are immigrating in numbers, causing an influx in cities where there are no longer jobs available. Even in informal settlements, it is still a common gesture

for men to go out and look for jobs, leaving their partners and wives at home; hence it is imperative that women should be seen to be playing a role in local economic development, by being involved in farming activities.

Van Averbeke (2007) reported that urban agriculture in Nigeria tended to be associated with lack of formal sector employment and aimed primarily at the production of food for home consumption, which enabled households to save on food expenditure. Van Averbeke further highlights the fact that besides providing food, urban farming performed other important functions, which are social, cultural, developmental, aesthetic and environmental.

In a study that was conducted by Van Averbeke on urban agriculture in the informal settlements, it is highlighted that women have to take a centre stage in developmental activities in order "to cope with problems of identity which affect them in particular, and because food production forms part of their traditional roles in family units." And for this reason, Van Averbeke suggests that interventions that promote urban agriculture for the purpose of improving human nutrition should target women.

Similarly, as urban expansion continues, the overall cost of supplying, distributing and accessing food is likely to increase as well as the number of households that are food insecure. Therefore, the challenges of feeding the cities lies in facilitating consumers access to food and ensuring that required investments are forthcoming for increasing food production, processing and distribution capacities and services under hygienic, health and environmentally sound conditions hence adequately meeting these challenges will promote the development of the peri-urban areas to feed the ever-grown cities (Olivio, 2000).

In view of the above situation, the study was carried out in Somolu Local Government Area of Lagos State with the aims to identify the personal characteristics of the women involved in urban agriculture as well as ascertaining the tasks or roles they perform in urban agriculture. It was hypothesized that, there was no significant relationship between respondents' personal characteristics and their attitude towards urban agriculture as a profession.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was carried out in Somolu Local Government Area of Lagos. It has a growing population of above 50,000 people with a total area of 3,000km² which lies within the humid tropical zone bounded in the north by Bariga Local Government, in the east by Fadeyi Local Government while in the south by Mushin Local Government and in the west by Ojuwoye Local Government area. Being an urban area, majority of the inhabitants are civil servants, also other income generating activities like tailoring, hair-dressing, trading etc can also be found in the area.

The population of the study consists of women farmers involved in urban agriculture. In the study area, five (5) extension blocks were purposively selected due to their agrarian background. Simple random sampling was used to consider thirty percent (30%) of respondents from the list of registered women farmers in the five selected extension blocks, forming a total of 50 women farmers considered for the study. The list of women involved in urban agriculture was provided by the ADP officials in the local government, containing 168 women farmers.

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analyses. The descriptive statistics used includes, frequency counts and percentages while the inferential statistics used for testing the relationship between the variable was chi-square.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Table 1 reveals that 84% of the respondents are within the age range of 1-40 years who are considered to be young, agile and active women farmers. On the average the respondents were 30.6 years old. This indicates that, the respondents were still very young, active and will have right attitude towards urban agriculture.

Further analysis reveals that majority of the respondents were married (60%) while 10% accounted for single respondents and the remaining 16% and 14% represent widowed and divorced respondents, respectively. This implies that more married women were unemployed and have a higher degree of dependence to cater for. Also, these dependants would provide the extra labour that would be required for the operations involved in urban agriculture. Similarly, majority of the women sampled (76%) have one form of education or the other while the remaining 24% have no formal education. This indicates that education helps women farmers to respond positively to challenges, innovation and other farming technologies which results to high productivity.

Also, 36% of the sampled respondents earn moderate income annually from the sales of produces obtained from the activities while 50% earn high income annually. Only 12% earns low annual income from the proceeds of their farms. This implies that the majority that earns higher annual income are better off than the others due to the fact that they have access to needed inputs and extension services. The table 1 further reveals that 74% of the sampled women cultivated between 0.5-1.0 acres of land only 2% cultivated between 4-5acres of

land. The remaining 24% have farm size ranging between 2-3acres. This implies that majority of the respondents involved in urban agricultural practices cultivate small piece of land which may be due to their not been able to have adequate access to farm land.

Similarly, majority of the respondents (70%) have between 1-7years of experience while 22% accounted for those respondents with above 8 years of experience and the remaining 8% have less than 9 years experience in urban agriculture. This implies that the higher the years of experience in urban agriculture the more knowledgeable in the techniques as well as rational in information utilization.

The table 1 further shows that half of the respondents (54%) do not have access to loan while 46% of the sampled respondents indicated that they have access to loan. This implies that the majority (50%) of the respondents who do not have access to loan may be as a result of their not having the needed and necessary collateral with which they can obtain loan from the bank coupled with high interest rate charged on the load. Moreso, over half of the respondents (96%) have access to input while only 4% do not have access to agriculture inputs.

**Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by their personal characteristics
N = 50**

Personal characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Age group (Years)		
< 20	04	8.0
20 – 30	15	30.0
31 – 40	23	46.0
41 and above	08	16.0
Mean age	30.6	
Marital status		
Single	05	10.0
Married	30	60.0
Divorced	07	14.0
Widowed	08	16.0
Educational level		
No formal education	12	24.0
Adult education	04	8.0
Primary education	08	16.0
Secondary education	16	32.0
Tertiary education	10	20.0
Farm size (acres)		
0.5 – 1.0	37	74.0
2.0 – 3.0	12	24.0
4.0 – 5.0	01	2.0
Years of experience		
< 1	04	8.0
1 – 3	16	32.0
4 – 7	19	38.0
8 and above	11	22.0
Annual income		
Low	06	12.0
Moderate	18	36.0
High	26	52.0
Access to loan		
Yes	23	46.0
No	27	54.0
Access to labour		
Yes	49	98.0
No	01	2.0
Access to input		
Yes	48	96.0
No	02	4.0

Source: Field Survey, 2010

Respondents level of interest to urban agriculture as a profession

Data presented on table 2 shows that majority of the women farmers sampled (34%) indicated that, they have high interest in urban agriculture even as a profession while 50% indicated moderate interest and 16% indicated low interest in urban agriculture. Women farmers, in the area, that had favourable attitude to urban agriculture were found to perform more in agricultural practices than those with lower attitude (unfavourable) score.

Table 2: Summary of trichotomized attitudinal scores

Attitude Score	Frequency	Percentage
High (Favourable)	17	34.0
Moderate (Neutral)	25	50.0
Low (Unfavourable)	08	16.0
Total	50	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2010.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Result presented in table 3 indicates that there exist a significant relationship between age of the respondents ($X^2_{cal} = 10.21$; $P < 0.05$); marital status ($X^2_{cal} = 9.08$; $P < 0.05$), access to loan ($X^2_{cal} = 5.09$; $P < 0.05$), years of experience ($X^2_{cal} = 12.41$; $P < 0.05$), educational level ($X^2_{cal} = 15.21$; $P < 0.05$) and their attitude towards urban agriculture. Similarly, it was discovered that no significant relationship exist between annual income ($X^2_{cal} = 7.02$; $P < 0.05$), access to labour ($X^2_{cal} = 3.01$; $P < 0.05$), farm size ($X^2_{cal} = 4.01$; $P < 0.05$), access to input ($X^2_{cal} = 2.22$; $P < 0.05$) and respondent attitude toward urban agriculture. This implies that educational level, age, access to loan, marital status and years of farming experience have positive influence on the respondents' attitudes to urban agriculture.

Table 3: Summary of the chi-square analysis of the relationship between selected personal characteristics of the respondents and their attitudes towards urban agriculture

Selected personal characteristics	X^2_{cal}	X^2_{tab}	Df	Remark
Age	10.21	7.81	2	S
Marital status	9.08	7.81	3	S
Educational level	15.21	11.07	4	S
Farm size	4.01	5.99	2	NS
Years of farming experience	12.41	7.81	3	S
Annual income	7.02	7.81	2	NS
Access loan	5.09	3.84	1	S
Access to labour	3.01	3.84	1	NS
Access to input	2.22	3.84	1	NS

At 5% level of significance

S: Significant

NS: Not Significant

CONCLUSIONS

The population of Somolu Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria is continually increasing, and has forced the rate of formal and public sector employment down. Therefore many urban dwellers must seek employment in the informal sector, making this an important source of income and food. Urban agriculture has become one of the most important informal sector practices for city dwellers.

The study reveals that there is a neutral attitude amongst women farmers in Somolu local government area of Lagos state. The neutral attitude is evidenced in their responses to urban agriculture questions asked in the interview guide. Though there is the recognition of the fact by the researchers that the responses are influenced by a myriad of extraneous factors, such as the psychological frame of mind, understanding of the question etc. by the farmer, the large sample size however, has helped to reduce the so called noises in the data set used for the

study. The low to neutral attitude is also attributable to ignorance on the part of the farmers as majority of them are not aware of the beneficial/or damaging effects of urban agriculture. The present levels of the women farmers (financial and knowledge) may not support the technicalities of certain practices towards ensuring sustainable urban agriculture practices. Based on these findings, the study recommends an increase in enlightenment campaign on agriculture, particularly on urban agriculture, an improvement in the supply of loan and access to production inputs such as chemical fertilizer to women farmers. Also, government policy must continue to be directed towards both improving the women irrespective of their age on the need to be involved in agriculture most especially in the urban areas i.e. making adequate use of available land in their vicinity to grow crops that can be sold in other to supplement their income and thus improving their standard of living and reducing the rate of unemployment.

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